

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Begmatova Sohiba Mustafaevna

NUCLEAR MEANS OF EXPRESSING THE LEXICO-SEMANTIC FIELD "HAPPINESS"

INSYSTEMS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

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★ ★ ★ ★ ★
HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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